

The Palit Relationship Applied to Polystyrene in Good, Poor and Intermediate Solvents

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Intrinsic viscosity data in good, poor and intermediate solvents have been treated utilizing the Palit equation. Palit's prediction that the differences in intrinsic viscosities in two different solvents is a linear function of $M^{2/3}$ has been confirmed.

TSIMPRIS *et al.*¹ recently reported the intrinsic viscosity-molecular weight relationship for polystyrene in N,N-dimethylformamide. Recently it was called to our attention that our data also fit an intrinsic viscosity-molecular weight relationship by Palit² and Sarker *et al.*³ which is based upon the Eyring rate theory and the whole theory of liquids:

$$100\rho[\eta] = K_1[M]^{2/3} - \ln M + K_2$$

where ρ is the partial specific density of polymer at infinite dilution.

K_1 and K_2 are constants.

A plot of $100\rho[\eta] + \ln M$ vs $M^{2/3}$ should be linear and the value of the constants K_1 and K_2 are obtained from the slope and intercept of the resulting line. Palit predicted the value of K_1 to be in the neighborhood of 10^{-2} .

Dilute solution data of polystyrene in a good, a poor and an intermediate solvent was treated by this equation.

Discussion

A plot of $100\rho[\eta] + \ln M$ against $M^{2/3}$ is shown in Figures 1, 2 and 3; the molecular weight of poly-

Fig. 1. Polystyrene in DMF, $A=0$ for 25° , $A=500$ for 35° , $A=1000$ for 45° .

styrene covering the range from 10^3 to 10^6 . The plot covers the range for a good solvent (toluene), a poor

Fig. 2. Polystyrene in toluene at 30° .

solvent (cyclohexane) and an intermediate solvent DMF (N,N-Dimethyl formamide). Palit^{2,4} pointed out that the value of ρ need not be very accurate and if partial specific density data are not available, the density of solid polymer could be used for the equation. In this case we choose ρ as the density of solid polystyrene i.e. 1.055. As shown in Figures 1, 2 and 3 this value of ρ gives a straight line within the range that the data cover. The resulting values of K_1 and K_2 are listed in Table 1.

The values of K_1 and K_2 in toluene agree with the values reported by Palit².

Palit² also showed that the difference in the intrinsic viscosities of a polymer in two different solvents is a linear function of $M^{2/3}$. We have confirmed this find as demonstrated in Table 2.

TABLE 1. VALUE FOR K_1 AND K_2 IN TOLUENE, CYCLOHEXANE AND DMF.

Solvent	Temp. °C	Range of Mw	$K_1 \times 10^2$	K_2	Data according to
Toluene	30.0	1.5×10^4 – 1.77×10^6	2.76	7.5	Luh ⁵
Cyclohexane	34.5	1.0×10^4 – 6.33×10^5	0.93	15.0	Luh ⁵
DMF	25–45	1.0×10^4 – 8.6×10^5	1.51	10.7	Tsimpris ¹ <i>et al.</i>

The Palit⁴ relationship has also been found to correlate with η -alkanes.

Fig. 3. Polystyrene in cyclohexane at 34.5°.

Fig. 4. Intrinsic viscosity difference of polystyrene in toluene and DMF; (O) Intrinsic viscosity difference of polystyrene in DMF and cyclohexane, (Δ).

TABLE 2. DILUTE SOLUTION DATA OF POLYSTYRENE IN CYCLOHEXANE AND DMF

Mw	a [η] cyclohexane	b [η] DMF	$\Delta[\eta] = [\eta]$ DMF-[η] cyclohexane
98,000	0.266	0.295	0.029
411,000	0.545	0.755	0.210
864,000	0.790	1.27	0.480

- a. Calculated from $[\eta] = 0.85 \times 10^{-3} \times M^{0.5}$ according to Kreju *et al.*
 b. Data from Luh⁵.

TABLE 3. DILUTE SOLUTION DATA OF POLYSTYRENE IN TOLUENE AND DMF

Mw	c [η] toluene	b [η] DMF	$\Delta[\eta] = [\eta]$ toluene-[η] DMF
10,000	0.095	0.085	0.010
98,000	0.458	0.295	0.163
411,000	1.256	0.755	0.501
864,000	2.123	1.271	0.852

- c. Calculated from $[\eta] = 0.1386 \times 10^{-3} \times M^{0.705}$ according to Luh⁵

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References

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